

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine

VOLUME 2
ISSUE 11

JANUARY-MARCH ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

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A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume II, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

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“NEONATAL INTENSIVE CARE UNIT”

In the NICU, lights are soft and low.
I watch a tiny heart strive to grow.
Her breath was so delicate, barely there.
Yet somehow filled with quiet dare.

A little hand curls into mine.
So small, so warm, so stubbornly fine.
I saw and held your endless dreams.
Now flicker faintly in gentle beams.

I whisper a hope, a silent prayer.
I wish my child could linger there.
Her monitors hum, steady and low.
Counting every rise, every slow fall below.

Some nights are quiet, some are full of fear.
I lean closer, so they know I'm near.
A tiny sigh, a struggling fight.
I stay awake with them through the night.

But sometimes love, no matter how strong.
Can't keep a fragile life for long.
And in that quiet, shadowed room.
A little soul loose into gentle gloom.

The hand that I held tight now let go.
The room feels heavy and slow.
And in the silence, sad and true.
A thousand hearts break quietly, too.

Though that breath has gone away.
The love it left will always stay.
Each child we care for after this.

Carries a memory, a tender kiss.

Little angels come and go,
Leaving behind more love than we know.
And in the NICU's dim, quiet light,
Their spirits linger—soft and bright.

